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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF LIPSTICK USING NATURAL COLORANTS

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ABSTRACT

Cosmetics have become one of the daily necessities of all groups in society every year, users were introduced to various new cosmetic products of the latest trend. Lipstick is one of the beauty product that commands a unique market. The quality of lipstick is directly linked to basic material use in the formulation. Natural ingredients based products are getting popular, as a public concerned toward long term effect of synthetic material in cosmetic formulation increased. In this work, natural colorants based lipsticks were produced. This formulation consists of oil mixtures, wax mixtures, bromo mixtures, colours, and other additives. It was prepared with beet root powder and natural food colour which gives pink colour as well as combination of cocoa powder, coffee and cinnamon gives chocolate brown colour. The lipstick were used previously contains organic colours which contain may harmful agents like lead, manganese, cadmium, etc. which are carcinogenic in nature and may lead to many side effects. By comparing both the combination one of the combination is better than other on the basis of appearance, colour, softening point and spreadability.

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INTRODUCTION:**WHAT IS LIPSTICK..???**

Lipstick is the cosmetic product containing pigments, oil waxes and emollients that apply colour, texture and protection of the lips. As we have seen synthetic colours are harmful and they may lead to various side effects like carcinogenicity. To prevent this harmful side effect we are tending towards more usage of natural colorants. There is following incidences/campaigns/research papers/test which shows adverse side effect of synthetic colorants in lipstick.

Every day millions of women apply lipstick without a second thought. What many don't know is that lipsticks may contain lead, the notorious metal that can cause learning, language and behavioural problems. Lead is a neurotoxin and can be dangerous even at small doses. Not all lipsticks contain lead, but a number of studies in recent years show that the metal is more prevalent than previously thought.

History

Ancient Sumerian men and women were possibly the first to invent and wear lipstick, about 5,000 years ago. They crushed gemstones and used them to decorate their faces, mainly on the lips and around the eyes. Also Egyptians like Cleopatra crushed bugs to create a colour of red on their lips. Also around 3000 BC to 1500 BC, women in the ancient Indus Valley Civilization applied red tinted lipstick to their lips for face decoration. Ancient Egyptians wore lipstick to show social status rather than gender. They extracted the red dye from fucus-algin, 0.01% iodine, and some bromine mannite, but this dye resulted in serious illness. Lipsticks with shimmering effects were initially made using a pearlescent substance found in fish scales.

In the 19th century, lipstick was colored with carmine dye. Carmine dye was extracted from cochineal, scale insects native to Mexico and Central America which live on cactus plants. Cochineal insects produce carminic acid to deter predation by other insects. Carminic acid, which forms 17% to 24% of the weight of the dried insects, can be extracted from the insect's body and eggs.

This lipstick did not come in a tube; it was applied with a brush. Carmine dye was expensive and the look of carmine colored lipstick was considered unnatural and theatrical, so lipstick was frowned upon for everyday wear. Only actors and actresses could get away with wearing lipstick. In 1880, few stage actresses wore lipstick in public.

Lipsticks are also term as lips cosmetics are widely used by woman. Lipstick have become so popular in the last couple of decades that they are now probably used more than any other single cosmetic product, its popularity can be gauged from the fact that market has been flooded with plenty of product with hundreds of sheds.

In this mini research project we are performing comparative study between lipstick and lip balm using natural colorants. Now days many brands has come up with lead free lipstick (e.g. Dior, Avon, MAC, Revelon, Tarte etc.) Natural colours are easily available with no side effect. In comparison with organic colours, they are more preferable and safe for use.

Ideal properties of lipstick are as follows:

- Smooth and easy to apply.
- High retention of colour intensity.
- Free from grittiness and bloom and should be non-drying.
- Required Plasticity.
- Innocuous externally as well as internally.
- Good degree of indelibility.
- Pleasant odour and flavour.
- Shiny appearance on storage.
- Remain firm on storage

MATERIALS AND METHOD:**MATERIAL**

Carnauba wax, ozokerite wax, Lanolin, Cetyl alcohol, Bess wax, and castor oil were purchased from S.D. Fine chemicals limited. All chemicals used for analysis were of analytical grade.

Formulation of lipstick:**-Wax mixtures:**

Are basically important as desired melting point, viscosity and other physical properties are achieved with different waxes. Example: hard paraffin, soft paraffin, white beeswax, cetyl alcohol, ozokerite wax, lanolin etc.

-Oil mixtures:

Act as dispersing agents for insoluble pigments. Castor oil is commonly used. Other examples are liquid paraffin-gives glossy appearance, isopropyl myristate, isopropyl palmitate, oleyl alcohol.

-Bromo mixtures:

Bromo acids dissolved in polyols like propylene glycol (400, 1500, 4000), benzyl alcohol, butylene glycol, oleyl alcohol, butyl stearate, etc..

-Colorants:

used are obtained from natural source:--Titanium dioxide is used to modify shade of basic pigment.

Additives include:**A Antioxidants:**

Butylated hydroxy toluene (BHT), butylated hydroxy anisole (BHA), propyl gallate, citric acid etc.

b. Preservatives:

Propyl parahydroxy benzoate

c. Flavours:

Should not be irritating and toxic, should have good taste and should be able to mask the fatty odour of the base

Manufacturing of lipsticks:

Involves 4 distinct operations:

- 1) Colour dispersion
- 2) Mixing
- 3) Moulding
- 4) Flaming.

Colour dispersion

- Agglomerates of colour pigments broken down and mixed with oil.
 - If a solvent is used for the preparation of solution of bromo acids, it is prepared and set aside.
 - Lake colours when used are dispersed in suitable amount of oil to make a paste. This paste can be passed through triple roller mills.
 - The colour mix is then mixed with bromo acid mixture.
 - Lower melting point waxes melted and added to the colour mix. Then additives are dissolved in remaining oil and mixed.
 - But higher melting point waxes are melted at the end.
 - The mixture should be finally milled
- Triple roller mill is used for colour dispersion

Figure: 1(A) Triple roller mill.

Figure:1(B) Triple roller mill (side view)

Mixing

- After milling, the material is transferred to a steam-jacketed kettle and is heated.
- Over-heating and rapid mixing should be avoided.
- After the mixture is melted completely and blended, perfume is added and blended thoroughly.
- Next the molten mixture is strained through fine mesh screen and transferred to moulds or storage containers.
- If the material is to be stored for a longer period, storage containers should be inert
- SS steam jacketed kettle is used for mixing

Figure:2: Stainless steel steam jacketed kettle.

Moulding:

- For moulding, operation moulds are used.
- Moulds are made up of metals like brass, aluminium.
- Molten lipstick mixture is run on the seat of the mould and the speed of pouring should be appropriate.
- The moulds are allowed to stand without movement until surplus material has congealed over the surface
- The surplus material is then scraped off and moulds are transferred to chilled metallic plates.
- Over-cooling should be avoided.
- Then moulds are unclamped and lipsticks are pushed out.
- When large production is required, semi-automatic or automatic moulding machines are used for this operation

Figure:3(A)-Filling of moulds

Figure:3(B):lipsticks ready to place

Figure:3(C)- Lipsticks

Flaming:

- The sticks are inserted in lipstick containers and the free end is reheated for a very short time.
- This makes the surface of the stick smooth and glossy.
- This process is usually done by passing the lipstick through gas flame.
- Finally the stick and containers are examined for visual defects

Figure:4-lipstick after flaming process and burner used.

Table number. :1 formula table:

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Quantity given	Quantity taken for 3 lipsticks (15 gm.)	Activity
1.	Carnauba wax	3%	0.45gm	Waxes
2.	Ozokerite wax	8%	1.2gm	Waxes
3.	Beeswax	8%	1.2gm	Film former
4.	Lanoline	10%	1.5gm	Emollient
5.	Castor oil	65%	9.75ml	Plasticizer
6.	Cetyl alcohol	5%	0.75ml	Emollient
7.	Natural colour	q.s.	q. s	Colorant
8.	Titanium dioxide	3%	q. s	Covering agent
9.	Perfume	q. s	q. s	Fragrance
10.	Preservative	0.05%	0.000075gm	Preservative

Procedure:

Clean lipstick mould was taken, lubrication is done with soap solution and excess lubricant was drained and it was kept inverted in fridge or on ice (for half an hour). Colour and titanium dioxide were mixed in glass mortar and pestle and they were passed through 100 mesh. Colour mixture was placed in small beaker and levigated with part of castor oil. In big beaker waxes, lanolin and remaining castor oil were taken. Colour phase and oil phase were heated to same temperature. Then oil phase was added to colour phase with stirring. Overfilling of the mould was done with melted mass. It was allowed to settle. Lipstick was passed through flame. The base was trimmed and lipsticks were packed in a holder.

EVALUATION TEST:

The basic requirements for a good lipstick are:

- 1) The lipstick shall be firm but not brittle in texture.
- 2) It shall have an attractive appearance, pleasant taste and feel on the lips and shall be reasonably free from sweating, bloom and rancidity.

Tests:

- 1) Appearance: it should be attractive
- 2) Softening point: Methods for evaluation of lipstick

Apparatus used:

- Flat bottom tube: 12cm long and 2.5 cm in diameter
- Thermometer: accurate to 0.1 C.

Figure:5 (A)-Beaker with thermometer inserted.

Figure:5(B) Flat bottom tube.

Procedure:

- Place the lipstick with protruded salve in the flat bottom tube. Fix the thermometer through a cork in such a way that the bulb of the thermometer just touches the lipstick salve. Insert this arrangement into a 1litre beaker filled with water to a level 1cm above the upper tip of the lipstick salve. Slowly heat the water while stirring so that temperature rises at a rate not exceeding 2°C per min.
- When the temperature reaches about 45°C, raise the temperature at the rate of 1° C per min. Constantly watch the lipstick salve.
- Record the temperature when the salve starts bending and loosing its shape
- Colour: In this colour imparting on the lip surface is observed
- Film: Type of film formed is observed
- Spread ability: spread ability of formulation is observed.

RESULT

Lipstick made up of beet root and natural food colour (A) is more better then cocoa powder, coffee and cinnamon(B) on the basis of Appearance, even colour dispersion, film, colour, spread ability and hardness

Table number: 2.

Test	Observation for combination of beet root and natural food colour (A)	Observation for combination of cocoa powder, coffee and cinnamon(B)
Appearance	Reddish pink	Chocolate brown
Softening point	56 degree	52 degree
Colour	Pink	Dark brown
Film	Greasy	Greasy
Spread ability	Easily spreadable as compare to B	Not easily spreadable as compare to A

Author's statement:

The authors declarers no conflict of interest.

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